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The Role of Customs and Tariff Regulation and Customs Control in Ensuring Economic Security of Kyrgyzstan

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Abstract

The article examines the role of customs and tariff regulation and customs control in ensuring the economic security of the country. It describes the main instruments of customs and tariff policy, including the establishment of customs duties, taxes, fees, quotas and licenses for the import and export of goods. It emphasizes the importance of a balance between protecting the domestic market and developing foreign economic relations. It also notes the need to take into account international obligations and international law when forming customs and tariff policy and implementing customs control.

The article examines the economic costs of Kyrgyzstan associated with violations in the sphere of foreign economic activity and customs regulation. The main focus is on problems at the stages of release of goods and post-customs control. To overcome the identified problems, comprehensive measures are proposed, including the development of methodological recommendations, training for employees, interaction with experts, automation of customs processes and the creation of an integrated database. The introduction of innovative simulators to improve the skills of employees is also mentioned. The purpose of the proposed measures is to improve the efficiency of customs control and create a transparent environment for participants in foreign economic activity, which should contribute to the economic development of Kyrgyzstan.

Keywords: economic security, customs authorities, foreign economic activity, customs tariff regulation, customs duties, customs tariffs, customs control.

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1. Introduction

As a result of changes in the economic sphere of Kyrgyzstan—including the transition to a market economy, the weakening of the monopoly in foreign trade, and the establishment of customs authorities as an independent state structure—a number of ministries and departments have transferred their powers and functions to these bodies.

Today, the customs service of Kyrgyzstan plays an important role in public administration. It has transformed itself from an executive authority dealing with foreign trade into a regulatory and law enforcement body. At the same time, the activities of customs authorities are unique and unparalleled, as they directly influence the country's economic security and the protection of its national interests. This is due to several reasons.

First, the contribution of customs duties to the state budget of the Kyrgyz Republic is significant. The country currently maintains active trade relations with more than 140 countries. On average, customs payments account for 44% of the state budget. Many socio-economic obligations of the government—such as poverty reduction, raising salaries for teachers and doctors, improving the quality of life for the population, and other aspects of social policy—depend on the volume of these revenues. For example, in the first quarter of 2025 alone, the State Customs Service of Kyrgyzstan (SCS) ensured the collection of customs payments amounting to 31.1 billion soms, which is 286.9 million soms above the planned figure [1].

Second, as part of the law enforcement system, the customs service contributes significantly to combating smuggling, customs-related crimes, and violations of customs regulations. For instance, starting in 2025, following the decision of the Committee on Law and Order, Crime Control and Anti-Corruption of the Jogorku Kenesh dated November 12, 2024, as well as directives from the Presidential Administration of the Kyrgyz Republic dated December 12, 2024 (Nos. 14-11319, 14-11320, and 14-11321), the State Customs Service under the Ministry of Finance of the Kyrgyz Republic (SCS), together with the Main Directorate for Road Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs (GUOBDD MIA), carried out a series of raids. The aim of these operations was to identify vehicles with state license plates that had been illegally imported and were being used within the Kyrgyz Republic. As a result, in March 2025, 959 cases were transferred to the SCS Investigation Department [2]. Furthermore, in February 2025 alone, customs enforcement units uncovered violations and crimes in the field of customs law amounting to a total of 40.9 million soms. Based on 557 initiated cases, fines totaling 3.48 million soms were collected, and customs payments in the amount of 27.6 million soms were made as part of preventive measures [3].

Given that international drug traffickers use Kyrgyzstan's territory to transport narcotics to Europe, the law enforcement function of the customs authorities becomes especially relevant.

Third, the intensive development of customs legislation has allowed customs authorities to expand their activities and solidify their status as a law enforcement agency. This has also provided momentum for the development of fiscal activities and customs control, increasing the efficiency in combating customs violations.

Fourth, the goal of modern customs policy is to facilitate integration into international economic relations through a financial and economic mechanism of state regulation, which includes tariff and non-tariff measures. Achieving this goal also requires the effective operation of customs authorities.

According to customs statistics on foreign trade with third countries, for January–February 2025, the foreign trade turnover of the Kyrgyz Republic amounted to 1,345.2 million US dollars. Compared to the same period in 2024 (1,710.73 million US dollars), the growth rate was 78.6% [4].

The aim of this study is to conduct a comprehensive analysis and identify gaps in the system of customs-tariff regulation and customs control as tools for ensuring Kyrgyzstan's economic security, and based on the findings, to develop practical recommendations for optimizing and improving this system.

2. Methodology

Currently, researchers in Kyrgyzstan are actively studying customs control and customs-tariff regulation from various perspectives—primarily financial, historical-legal, and administrative-legal. However, within economic theory, a comprehensive and systematic analysis of this phenomenon—one that takes into account its patterns and challenges in the context of integration processes and national economic security—has been scarcely conducted. The limited body of work by domestic scholars is generally fragmented and addresses only specific aspects of customs activities. While the existing academic contributions in this field are undoubtedly valuable, they require reconsideration in light of the current socio-economic and political-legal realities.

Accordingly, the study of the theoretical and practical key aspects of the functioning of customs authorities, as well as the mechanisms for their implementation, is particularly significant in terms of enhancing their effectiveness.

The methodological foundation of this study includes both general scientific and specialized methods of knowledge acquisition. During the analysis of customs control practices implemented by the customs authorities, the methods of system analysis and synthesis, theoretical modeling, and formal-logical reasoning were applied. In the process of preparing this publication, hypothesis-building methods were also used, which helped to identify both theoretical and applied issues in customs control under current conditions.

3. Results

3.1. Analysis of Customs-Tariff Regulation Mechanisms as a Factor of Kyrgyzstan's Economic Security

Determining the tools of trade policy and methods of state regulation of foreign economic activity is a vital task. Researchers analyze tariff and non-tariff measures, classifying them into economic and administrative categories. Customs-tariff regulation occupies a central place in managing foreign trade operations, with the customs tariff serving as a key economic instrument. Through customs-tariff regulation, the state influences foreign trade and the economy as a whole.

Tariff-based customs regulation performs several key functions. First, it protects the domestic market by restricting the import of competing goods through high import duties. Second, tariff methods stimulate the development of national industry by lowering the cost of exported goods through preferential rates. Lastly, they play an important role in fiscal policy, serving as a source of government revenue used to finance state programs. Thus, tariff regulation not only protects national interests but also promotes economic growth. It is a tool for regulating foreign economic activity that can both shield domestic producers and foster free trade. Protectionist measures aim to restrict imports and support local producers, while liberal tariffs encourage open trade and imports, potentially lowering prices and improving product quality for consumers.

In today's global economy, tariff methods are also essential for international economic relations, trade agreements, and dispute resolution.

There are three main types of tariff rates: **ad valorem**, **specific**, and **combined**. Each has its own characteristics and is applied depending on the context and objectives of trade policy.

- **Ad valorem tariffs**, based on the value of the goods, are calculated as a percentage of the customs value. For example, if a product costs \$1,000 and the ad valorem rate is 10%, the duty will be \$100. These tariffs are commonly used to protect the domestic market and stimulate local production. The higher the value of imports, the less profitable they become.
- **Specific tariffs** are set as a fixed amount per unit, regardless of the product's value. For example, a \$50-per-barrel tariff on oil applies regardless of its market price. These tariffs are typically applied to goods that are difficult to value (e.g., raw materials or energy resources).
- **Combined tariffs** include elements of both ad valorem and specific tariffs, creating a more flexible import regulation system. For instance, a tariff might be set at 10% of the product's value but not less than \$100 per unit. This system protects the market from cheap imports without

harming high-value goods. Combined tariffs also help ensure stability in trade relations. The predictability of duty rates reduces risks for participants in foreign trade [5, p. 31].

In other words, tariffs are a system of rates and rules under which customs duties are applied. The formation of tariffs depends on a number of factors, including government budget regulation, differentiated subsidies and benefits, political and economic sanctions. These factors significantly impact the economic situation, social policy, and international relations. The Foreign Economic Activity Commodity Nomenclature takes all these factors into account and serves as the basis for classifying goods and services, which is essential for tracking and regulating foreign economic activities. Adjusting tariffs in line with the nomenclature ensures the stability of the domestic market and enhances economic competitiveness, allowing the state to manage economic processes effectively and support strategically important industries.

Thus, customs-tariff policy creates a balanced foreign trade structure, stimulates investment, and helps control inflation. In 2024, Kyrgyzstan's foreign trade turnover reached \$16 billion. According to the National Statistics Committee, the trade balance showed moderate growth due to increased exports and expanded imports [6]. The main export items included:

- gold (\$1.4 billion),
- knitwear and textiles (\$94 million),
- agricultural products (\$72 million),
- energy resources, and others.

The top imported goods included passenger vehicles, dishwashers and washing machines, petroleum products, gasoline, and agricultural machinery for harvesting and threshing [7].

Thus, tariff measures are a fundamental component of customs policy, regulating the foreign economic activity of the Kyrgyz Republic and protecting its national interests. The **customs tariff** represents a structured list of customs duty rates for goods crossing the state border of Kyrgyzstan. This classification helps to standardize customs procedures and make them more transparent for all participants.

Customs duty is essentially a form of rent reflecting the surplus income obtained when goods are purchased on the world market at a price lower than the cost of producing them domestically. The state captures part of this savings for its own benefit. Rational use of this revenue involves directing it toward the country's socio-economic development. Unlike other taxes, customs duties are levied exclusively on participants in foreign economic activity—importers or exporters—regardless of the end consumer [5, p. 9]. Low export duties help increase the volume of exports and the income of exporters. Customs duties are designed to reflect the price gap between global and domestic markets. In cases where domestic production exists, the duty depends on the cost difference between global and national production. The main goal is to objectively reflect that gap [5, p. 18].

As of **April 1, 2024**, Kyrgyzstan introduced new rules for duty-free import of goods for personal use. For goods brought in by land transport or on foot, the duty-free limit is €500 and 25 kg. For goods delivered by mail or express courier services, the limit is €200 and 31 kg [8]. In **July 2024**, the government introduced new rules regarding customs fees related to customs operations. The fee rate is 0.4% of the customs value of goods. The minimum fee is **5 settlement units**, and the maximum is **2,500 settlement units** [9].

Under conditions of global economic decline and increasing protectionist measures—including sanctions—customs-tariff policy faces serious challenges such as disrupted supply chains and a worsening investment climate [10, p. 67]. In these circumstances, customs-tariff regulation in Kyrgyzstan should aim to ensure balanced foreign trade turnover, enhance the competitiveness of domestic producers, and optimize the structure of international trade within the framework of integration processes such as the **EAEU**, **SCO**, and other international organizations. The volume of mutual trade between Kyrgyzstan and other EAEU members is clearly illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. – Volume of Kyrgyzstan's Mutual Trade with EAEU Member States (Million USD)

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
EAEU Member States:	2 439.8	3 426.4	4 774.1	4 599.2	4 975.3
Armenia	5.3	3.5	6	4.2	1.8
Belarus	47.8	74	111.4	117	97.1
Kazakhstan	809.5	1 044	1 181.1	1 371.4	1 329.5
Russia	1 577.2	2 304.9	3 475.7	3 106.6	3 546.9

Note: Data from the official website of the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic (NSC KR) – www.stat.kg.

From the presented data, it can be concluded that the volume of Kyrgyzstan's mutual trade with the EAEU member states shows a growth trend. Trade with Armenia fluctuates, starting at 5.3 million USD in 2020 and decreasing to 1.8 million USD in 2024. Trade with Belarus also demonstrates growth: from 47.8 million USD in 2020 to 97.1 million USD in 2024. Trade with Kazakhstan increases from 809.5 million USD in 2020 to 1,329.5 million USD in 2024. Trade with Russia shows significant growth: from 1,577.2 million USD in 2020 to 3,546.9 million USD in 2024. Thus, it can be noted that the overall trade volume of Kyrgyzstan with the EAEU countries is growing, but the trade dynamics with individual countries differ noticeably. The main trading partner of Kyrgyzstan is Russia, followed by neighboring Kazakhstan.

Customs-tariff regulation includes stimulating investment activity, including attracting foreign direct investment. The main tasks of customs-tariff policy include controlling the growth of domestic prices, ensuring the sustainable filling of the state budget, and reducing direct and indirect costs for participants in foreign economic activity. At the same time, for example, the countries of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) currently face a number of problems in customs-tariff regulation. One of the key problems is the need to modernize customs legislation. There is a need for a clear distinction between supranational regulation, which is enshrined in the EAEU Customs Code, and national regulation of foreign economic activity, which is governed by the legislation of the union member states.

Membership in the EAEU limits the ability of national states to independently influence the volumes of foreign trade through customs-tariff mechanisms. This requires harmonization of national tools with supranational ones, which can lead to contradictions and reduce the effectiveness of customs-tariff regulation as a factor in economic development. Another issue is the low level of differentiation in the rates of the Common Customs Tariff. More than 4/5 of the tariff consists of ad valorem rates, which primarily protect product groups that are not key to the innovative development of the EAEU.

To address this issue, it is proposed to increase the number of specific and combined tariffs, which will make the customs policy more flexible and less fiscally oriented. There is also a decrease in the degree of tariff protection for the domestic market against imports. Rates on technical components are being reduced, and in some cases, they are eliminated altogether, for example, on fish roe and cashew nuts. The tariff escalation tool is not used, which leads to uniformity of rates for various product categories. All of this creates risks for the budget, weakens protectionism, increases imports, and, as a result, slows down economic growth.

3.2. Customs Control as a Tool for Protecting the Economic Interests of Kyrgyzstan

Customs tariff regulation and customs control complement each other and ensure effective management of foreign economic activity, protection of national interests, and stimulation of economic development. The link between customs tariff regulation and customs control lies in the fact that customs payments are one of the main tools for regulating foreign economic activity. The establishment of tariffs and taxes affects the volume of imports and exports, as well as the choice of routes for the movement of goods. In turn, customs control ensures compliance with the established rules and norms when goods cross the border. This helps prevent illegal import and export of goods and ensures the timely and complete collection of customs payments.

In the Kyrgyz Republic, customs control is carried out by the State Customs Service, which is the key executive body in this area. Subordinated to the Government of the country, the State Customs Service plays a crucial role in ensuring the economic security of the state, regulating foreign economic activity, and protecting the domestic market.

The State Customs Service includes various divisions and regional customs offices, each performing a range of functions. Among them, the "Manas" customs office, located at the Manas Airport, stands out as a key point for the passage of international cargo and passengers. Additionally, the "Osh" Customs Processes Center coordinates and manages customs processes in the southern part of the country.

The primary tasks of the customs service include monitoring the movement of goods across the border, collecting customs payments, conducting inspections and cargo examinations, and fighting smuggling and violations of customs regulations.

Experts propose several approaches to classify customs control, which help systematize methods and optimize the process. Depending on the subject of control, customs control can be classified into control of goods, vehicles, documents, and individuals. Each of these types of control requires specific methods. For instance, the control of goods involves verifying the accuracy of the declared data, while the control of vehicles involves inspecting documents confirming the right to transport goods. The type of transportation significantly influences the organization of transportation and, accordingly, the inspections. Road transportation is suitable for short distances but requires regular maintenance and adherence to road traffic rules. Rail transportation ensures safety and speed for long distances, but requires careful cargo preparation. Air transportation is convenient for long distances but has volume and weight restrictions.

Table 2. – Freight Transport by Types of Transport in Kyrgyzstan, Million Tons

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Total	30	34.2	44.3	51	54.1
Rail Transport, Thousand Tons	7 306.5	7 660.5	8 022	9 367	9 184
Road Transport	22.4	26.2	35.9	41.3	44.4
Pipeline Transport, Thousand Tons	256.9	305.4	336.5	355.7	442.8
Water Transport, Thousand Tons	–	–	–	–	–
Air Transport, Thousand Tons	0.1	0.4	0.3	13.9	44.8

Note: Data from the official website of the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic (NSC KR) – www.stat.kg.

As can be seen from the data provided, the total volume of cargo transportation has gradually increased from 30 million tons in 2020 to 54.1 million tons in 2024. This indicates an overall growth in cargo transportation. Rail transport shows a steady increase in the volume of transportation: from 7,306.5 thousand tons in 2020 to 9,184 thousand tons in 2024, which signifies that rail transport remains an important method for cargo delivery. Road transport also shows growth: from 22.4 thousand tons in 2020 to 44.4 thousand tons in 2024. This may be linked to the increase in “door-to-door” delivery volumes in urban and regional logistics chains. Air transport also demonstrates significant growth in cargo volumes, from almost zero in 2020 to 44.8 thousand tons in 2024, suggesting an expansion in the use of air transport for delivering certain types of goods requiring high-speed delivery. Overall, the statistical data indicates the development of transportation infrastructure and the growth in cargo transportation during the period in question.

Control methods are adapted to the type of transport, including modern technologies that allow tracking goods in real-time. Customs control can be either documentary or physical. Documentary control involves the process of checking customs declarations, certificates of quality, and other documents and information for compliance with current legislation. Its goal is to identify illegal trade, violations of licensing conditions, and economic crimes. Physical control, on the other hand, includes inspecting goods, vehicles, and containers. This type of customs control allows for the detection of discrepancies in data, signs of smuggling, and forged documents, as well as ensuring the proper conditions for transportation.

Both types of control complement each other, ensuring comprehensive security for foreign trade activities. Modern technologies such as automated risk management systems, scanning, and artificial intelligence significantly enhance their effectiveness.

A comprehensive approach to conducting inspection activities allows for flexible adjustments in the range of goods, leading to more accurate and justified results. This approach also involves a wide range of competent authorities, including representatives from various government bodies. Especially effective is the cooperation of customs, border, and tax authorities, facilitated by the creation of a unified payment administration mechanism. Joint inspections are carried out when there is reason to believe that foreign trade participants are violating tax, currency, or customs laws. These activities are coordinated in terms of timing and objects and can

be carried out either on a scheduled or unscheduled basis. Special attention is given to the exchange of information between customs and tax authorities to implement measures to counter tax evasion, which is particularly relevant in the context of digitalization of the economy and the introduction of information technologies in the work of customs and tax bodies.

In 2024, the State Customs Service collected customs duties (taxes and fees) amounting to 123,085.8 million soms, which is 101.7% of the planned amount (an over-fulfillment of 2,085.8 million soms). Compared to the same period last year, customs payment receipts increased by 10.4%, or 11,577.6 million soms. This growth is attributed to the modernization of the customs service, including the optimization of business processes, increased capacity at border crossing points, the introduction of digital technologies, and strengthened control over smuggling.

The execution of the customs payment plan for 2024 by sources was as follows:

- Receipts of VAT on goods imported into Kyrgyzstan from third countries amounted to 74,701.3 million soms, which corresponds to 102.4% of the plan. Compared to 2023, receipts decreased by 9.3% in 2024;
- Receipts from excise duties on goods imported from third countries reached 1,327.4 million soms, exceeding the plan by 9.1%. Compared to 2023, they grew 1.6 times;
- Receipts from taxes on international trade and foreign operations amounted to 41,983.9 million soms, which corresponds to 101% of the plan. The growth rate compared to the same period in 2023 was 148.1%. Specifically, import customs duties under the EAEU amounted to 25,595.6 million soms, with a growth rate of 100.4%.

To improve its performance, the State Customs Service is actively implementing modern technologies and automated systems. For example, electronic declarations accelerate the process of goods clearance and reduce the likelihood of errors. Risk management systems help identify potential threats and violations, optimizing resource allocation and improving control.

Customs inspection zones are being created along the border, at customs clearance locations, and where customs authorities are located. Access to these zones is only allowed with the permission of customs, except in cases provided by law. Persons crossing the border with goods are required to provide the necessary documents and information. Documents must be kept for at least three years. For assistance in control, customs authorities may involve specialists from other agencies. A request to involve such experts is mandatory for execution.

Customs officers also have the right to access areas and premises where goods under customs control are located, except in cases provided by law. Goods and transport can be identified through seals, stamps, markings, labels, photographs, and other means. Alteration or destruction of identification means is possible only with the permission of customs.

An essential tool for promoting domestic goods on foreign markets is technical regulation. Changes in the field of technical regulation in the Kyrgyz Republic are related to the implementation of the WTO Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade, the transition to voluntary standardization, the development and establishment of safety requirements in technical regulations, the establishment of conformity assessment forms that meet market requirements, and the reduction of administrative barriers. The most applied controls in Kyrgyzstan are sanitary, phytosanitary, and veterinary controls. Stricter controls are typically applied to food products, medicines, etc.

The greatest economic damage to the state is caused by the actions of foreign trade participants, such as undeclared goods, underreporting customs value, submission of counterfeit documents, movement of goods without documents, improper operations with goods, changing their condition, using deceptive identification methods, false declarations, submission of false information, and non-payment of customs duties. To this end, the Law of the Kyrgyz Republic "On Customs Regulation" (April 24, 2019 No. 52) granted customs authorities the right to collect "information about individuals engaged in foreign economic activity related to the movement of goods across the customs border or other activities concerning goods under customs control" (Part 1, Article 151), as well as within their competence "to hold individuals accountable for violations in accordance with the legislation of the Kyrgyz Republic on violations" (Part 2, Article 156).

One of the problems is the release of goods at customs, which is the next step after customs control and involves accounting, monitoring, and ensuring compliance with legislation in the area of foreign economic activity. The main tasks of this stage include verifying the use of goods for their declared purposes, conducting audits to detect violations, maintaining records, preparing reports, and reviewing complaints. Post-release of goods is crucial to ensure adherence to customs rules and the protection of the state's economic interests. For instance, since 1994, China has had a post-customs audit system that monitors compliance with legislation in warehouses and by all foreign trade participants, including enterprises and customs brokers. The audit includes checking payment of duties, the presence of goods in warehouses, and controlling the activities of customs representatives.

In Japan, post-customs audits are conducted for foreign trade participants who have paid customs duties of more than one million yen. The audit takes place within five years after the goods are released. There are two types of audits: general, which include checking all declarations for two years, and simplified, which involves selective checking. The list of "controlled importers" is updated monthly based on the risk level.

The main issues identified by specialists include:

- Insufficient methodological support for customs control after the release of goods;
- Corruption risks;
- Insufficient regulation of the customs value control procedure for post-customs control purposes.

To solve the problem of a lack of methodological materials for customs control after the release of goods, it is necessary to develop and regularly update instructions and manuals for customs officers. These documents may include action algorithms, typical inspection scenarios, and calculation examples that will help specialists perform their duties effectively. It is also important to conduct regular training and seminars for officers to familiarize them with new methods and approaches. Cooperation with external experts, such as auditors or consultants, could be an important tool for developing and implementing new control methods. Additionally, analyzing practices in other countries can help adapt effective methods for improving local processes.

The use of automation systems in post-release control is also important to accelerate the verification process and reduce the likelihood of errors. Creating a unified database containing information on violations and problems identified during control will allow for further analysis and the development of measures to prevent them. It should be noted that the Customs Training Academy, following the Development Concept for 2024-2026 and annual training plans, regularly conducts training to improve the qualifications of customs officers and other government agencies in Kyrgyzstan. Customs officers are continuously trained in recognizing and analyzing images using the Inspection and Scanning Complex (IDC) "ST-6035." As part of the short-term action plan for the GTS of the Ministry of Finance of the Kyrgyz Republic for 100 days, approved by Order No. 35-06/75 on March 5, 2025, the introduction of a simulator designed to emulate the work of IDC is planned. The Customs Training Academy suggested this idea as such a simulator would significantly improve the efficiency of officer training in image analysis, enhancing non-intrusive vehicle inspection and detecting smuggling. To combat corruption during customs procedures, the GTS has strengthened control, and a special "Trust Window" (<https://customs.gov.kg/site/ru/master/customskg/korrupcijaga-karshy>) was created on its official website, allowing citizens and foreigners who encounter corruption at customs checkpoints to submit complaints. All citizen complaints are processed, strengthening the monitoring and control system, including conducting regular checks. Additionally, improving transparency in procedures and publishing information about decision-making criteria and procedures will also help. However, since the customs service is a law enforcement agency (<https://customs.gov.kg/site/ru/master/customskg>), such information is not publicly available.

The development and implementation of a comprehensive set of anti-corruption measures, including preventive activities and investigations of corruption cases, are crucial steps in combating this phenomenon. Active cooperation with law enforcement agencies to identify and prevent corruption schemes in customs authorities will significantly enhance efforts to tackle

corruption. Creating conditions in which employees are less susceptible to corruption schemes, such as offering decent wages and social guarantees, will also help reduce corruption levels.

To address the issue of insufficient regulation of the customs value control procedure for post-control purposes, several measures can be taken. First, it is necessary to develop typical algorithms for checking customs value at the post-control stage. These algorithms should include a list of documents and information to be checked, as well as methods for calculating and comparing customs value with market prices. Secondly, training seminars and workshops for customs officers should be organized to familiarize them with new methodological recommendations and algorithms for checking. This will increase their qualifications and ensure better quality control. Thirdly, it is important to establish a constructive dialogue with foreign trade participants to encourage them to provide more complete and accurate information about the customs value of goods. Moreover, the introduction of modern information technologies, such as automatic data analysis systems and machine learning, can aid in more efficient customs value control. These technologies can be used to detect anomalies and suspicious transactions, thereby improving post-control effectiveness.

Finally, regular monitoring and analysis of post-control practices will help identify weaknesses and problematic areas that require further regulation, allowing for timely adjustments to methodological recommendations and legislation. If necessary, independent experts and consultants with experience in customs value and foreign economic activity can be involved. Their opinions and recommendations can help develop more effective post-control procedures.

4. Conclusion

Customs-tariff regulation and customs control are fundamental elements of government policy aimed at ensuring the economic security of the country. They serve as crucial tools for regulating foreign trade flows, protecting the domestic market from unfair competition, and ensuring compliance with foreign economic activity laws.

Customs-tariff policy includes the establishment of customs duties, taxes, and fees, as well as the determination of quotas and licenses for the import and export of goods. These measures allow the state to influence the volume and structure of foreign trade turnover and the level of prices in the domestic market. However, in the context of the current global economic downturn and the strengthening of protectionist trends, customs-tariff regulation should aim to ensure the balance of foreign trade turnover, increase the competitiveness of domestic producers, and optimize the structure of international trade.

The main goals of customs-tariff policy include curbing domestic price growth, ensuring a stable state budget, and reducing direct and indirect costs for participants in foreign economic activity. One of the key issues in customs-tariff regulation within the framework of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) is the need to modernize customs legislation and clearly delineate between supranational and national regulation.

Customs control aims to ensure compliance with customs legislation and prevent illegal movement of goods across borders. It involves checking documents and information, inspecting goods and vehicles, and applying other forms of control, including non-intrusive.

Effective customs-tariff regulation creates favorable conditions for the economy, protects the interests of producers and consumers, and ensures national security. However, excessive tightening of customs control measures can reduce the competitiveness of domestic goods and increase prices for imports. It is essential to strike a balance between protecting the domestic market and fostering foreign economic relations.

Furthermore, customs-tariff regulation and customs control should take into account the country's international commitments and norms of international law. This is especially important in the context of globalization and the integration of national economies into the global economic system.

Thus, customs-tariff regulation and customs control play a key role in ensuring the economic security of Kyrgyzstan, helping the government manage foreign economic activity, protect the domestic market, stimulate the economy, and ensure stable budget revenues.

References

- The Customs Service collected over 31 billion soms in the first quarter of 2025 [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://economist.kg/dengi/...32c745680234> (Accessed: 10.04.25).
- Results of the activities of the Main Directorate for Combating Smuggling of the State Customs Service of the Kyrgyz Republic for February 2025 [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://customs.gov.kg/site/ru/master/customskg/kontrabanda-menen-krsh> (Accessed: 28.03.25).
- Express information / Prepared by the Customs Statistics Department of the State Customs Service under the Ministry of Finance of the Kyrgyz Republic [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://docs.yandex.ru/...rtf&nosw=1> (Accessed: 10.04.25).
- Foreign trade turnover of the Kyrgyz Republic with third countries [Electronic resource]. - URL: <https://docs.yandex.ru/docs/view?url=ya-...xlsx&nosw=1> (access date: 12.04.25).
- Timofeeva E. (2019) Customs payments: a textbook for universities / E. Timofeeva. St. Petersburg: IC «Intermedia», 432 p.
- External trade turnover of Kyrgyzstan: analysis, trends and prospects [Electronic resource]. – URL: <https://eurasiatoday.ru/vneshnij-tovarooborot-kyrgyzstana-v-2024-godu-analiz-tendentsii-i-perspektivy/> (Accessed: 16.04.25).
- Trade geography of Kyrgyzstan: what the republic exported and bought in 2024: review [Electronic resource]. – URL: <https://economist.kg/all/2025/02/20/torghovaia-ghieoghrafiia-kyrgyzstana-chtok-eksportirovala-i-pokupala-riepublika-v-2024-ghodu-obzor/> (Accessed: 14.04.25).
- Reducing the threshold for duty-free import to the Kyrgyz Republic: market protection or burden for buyers? [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://economist.kg/exclusive/2024/06/07/snizhnyi-poroghabiesposhlinnogho-vvoza-v-kr-zashchita-rynka-ili-naghruzka-dlia-pokupateli/> (Accessed: 14.04.25).
- The Government of Kyrgyzstan introduced customs duties for the customs transit of goods [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://news.ati.su/news/2024/08/09/pravitelstvo-kyrgyzstana-vvelo-tamozhennye-sbory-za-tamozhennyj-tranzit-tovarov-683252/> (Accessed: 14.04.25).
- Gomon I.V., Belopkhova N.V (2019). Study of customs and tariff regulation in international economic relations. Natural-humanitarian research. № 26 (4), p. 66-71.
- Report on the execution of the republican budget for 2024 as part of the state budget [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://minfin.kg/posts/show/otchet-ob-ispolnenii-gosudarstvennogo-byudzhetakyrgy> (Accessed: 21.04.25).
- On Customs Regulation: Law of the Kyrgyz Republic dated April 24, 2019 № 52 (As amended by the Law of the Kyrgyz Republic dated August 9, 2023 № 172) // Erkin-Too. 2019. April 30.
- Ivanova, Y., Kuroptev, N (2021) Experience and Features of Customs Control after the Release of Goods in Foreign Countries. Bulletin of Innovative Technologies. Vol. 5. № 1 (17), Pp. 24-29.
- Yarullin, R.R. (2020) Features of Customs Control at the Present Stage: Problems and Prospects. International Journal of Humanities and Natural Sciences. Vol.1-2 (40). Pp. 163-166.